

Appendix A

Context parameters of the city and WM system

Context parameters Category	Context parameters Sub-category	Options
Basic city context	City size and population	<input type="checkbox"/> Megalopolis (> 10 million residents) <input type="checkbox"/> Conurbation (3-10 million residents) <input type="checkbox"/> Metropolis (1-3 million residents) <input type="checkbox"/> City (large city) (300 000 - 1 million residents) <input type="checkbox"/> Prefecture (medium city) (100 000 - 300 000 residents) <input type="checkbox"/> Borough (small city) (10 000 - 100 000 residents) <input type="checkbox"/> Medium town (1 000 - 10 000 residents) <input type="checkbox"/> Small town (> 1 000 residents)
	Climate	<input type="checkbox"/> Tropical (every month of the year with an average temperature of 18 °C or higher, with significant precipitation) <input type="checkbox"/> Dry (no month with an average temperature greater than 10 °C) <input type="checkbox"/> Temperate (the coldest month averaging between 0 °C and 18 °C and at least one month averaging above 10 °C) <input type="checkbox"/> Continental (at least one month averaging below 0 °C and at least one month averaging above 10 °C) <input type="checkbox"/> Polar (every month of the year with an average temperature below 10 °C)
Existing Waste Management (WM) infrastructure	Mark the physical infrastructure for waste management that the city has	<input type="checkbox"/> Garbage bins <input type="checkbox"/> Waste trucks <input type="checkbox"/> Points of intermediate waste storage <input type="checkbox"/> Control Station (dispatchers) <input type="checkbox"/> Plant / Factory: Waste disposal <input type="checkbox"/> Plant / Factory: Waste recycling <input type="checkbox"/> Plant / Factory: Waste valorization (mechanical, physical, thermal) <input type="checkbox"/> Plant / Factory: Waste treatment <input type="checkbox"/> Point of waste collection (Dump) <input type="checkbox"/> Pipes for transporting waste <input type="checkbox"/> All of the above <input type="checkbox"/> None of the above
	Is there a separate waste collection in the city?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
	Is separate waste collection available in all areas of the city?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Separate collection of some types of waste is everywhere, separate collection of some types of waste is not available in all areas <input type="checkbox"/> Separate waste collection does not work in all areas of the city
WM technologies	What city-level WM services are used in the city?	<input type="checkbox"/> Smart garbage bins <input type="checkbox"/> IoT devices on garbage trucks <input type="checkbox"/> IoT devices for waste sorting <input type="checkbox"/> Waste classification / segregation <input type="checkbox"/> Optimization of the planning of waste collection operations: Route planning <input type="checkbox"/> Optimization of the planning of waste collection operations: Route optimization <input type="checkbox"/> Optimization of the planning of waste collection operations: Scheduling <input type="checkbox"/> Optimization of the planning of waste collection operations: SGB positioning <input type="checkbox"/> Optimization of the planning of waste collection operations: Door-to-Door Garbage Collection <input type="checkbox"/> On-demand emptying of housing waste bins <input type="checkbox"/> User support: City Dashboard (Map) <input type="checkbox"/> User support: Notifications for drivers <input type="checkbox"/> User support: Information support for other stakeholders <input type="checkbox"/> User support: Complaints and reviews for citizens <input type="checkbox"/> Environment: Measure Environmental parameters <input type="checkbox"/> Environment: Minimize Carbon Emissions <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring the quantity and Quality of household waste using technologies <input type="checkbox"/> All of the above <input type="checkbox"/> None of the above

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	What Smart Garbage Bin (SGB) level WM services are used in the city?	<input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring: Show bins on the Map <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring: Video monitoring <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring: Fill level <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring: Weight <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring: GPS <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring: Temperature <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring: Humidity <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring: Moisture <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring: Gas (CO, NO2) <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring: Air quality <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring: SGB Lid control <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring: Metal <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring: Rain <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring: Person detection <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring: Existence of harmful materials and gases <input type="checkbox"/> Identification and classification: SGB identification <input type="checkbox"/> Identification and classification: Waste type identification <input type="checkbox"/> Identification and classification: Individual waste amount <input type="checkbox"/> Identification and classification: Person identification: Waste classification / segregation (SGB level) <input type="checkbox"/> All of the above <input type="checkbox"/> None of the above
Stakeholders	Mark primary and secondary stakeholders, involved in waste management process	<input type="checkbox"/> Primary Stakeholders: Citizen <input type="checkbox"/> Primary Stakeholders: Driver <input type="checkbox"/> Primary Stakeholders: Waste collection company <input type="checkbox"/> Primary Stakeholders: Dispatcher of waste collection company <input type="checkbox"/> Primary Stakeholders: Janitor <input type="checkbox"/> Primary Stakeholders: City administration <input type="checkbox"/> Primary Stakeholders: Municipality/ District administration <input type="checkbox"/> Primary Stakeholders: Waste trucks owning company <input type="checkbox"/> Primary Stakeholders: Waste department <input type="checkbox"/> Primary Stakeholders: Waste disposal organization <input type="checkbox"/> Primary Stakeholders: Waste recycling company <input type="checkbox"/> Primary Stakeholders: Waste treating company <input type="checkbox"/> Primary Stakeholders: Dump (Dump manager) <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary Stakeholders: Police <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary Stakeholders: Firefighters <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary Stakeholders: Municipal corporation <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary Stakeholders: Production center <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary Stakeholders: Health/environmental emergencies management organization <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary Stakeholders: Farmer <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary Stakeholders: Volunteer <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary Stakeholders: Recycling industry <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary Stakeholders: Disposal industry <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary Stakeholders: Food industry <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary Stakeholders: Healthcare <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary Stakeholders: Research <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary Stakeholders: Environment protection and related organizations <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary Stakeholders: Tourism industry
Financial aspects	What is the city's annual budget for tasks related to waste management? (€)	[Numeric]
	What is the annual city budget for solving current waste management related problems? (€)	[Numeric]
	What is the average income of the citizens? (€)	[Numeric]

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Residents awareness	Level of stakeholders Awareness and Engagement in Waste Management activities	[Rating from 1 to 5, where: 1 — Unaware — This is the lowest level of stakeholder engagement. Unaware stakeholders are not aware of the activity and its potential impacts. 2 — Resistant — This level of stakeholder engagement defines those who are aware of the activity and potential impacts, but are resistant to change or hesitant to get involved. 3 — Neutral — These stakeholders are aware of the activities but are neither supportive nor resistant. 4 — Supportive — Supportive stakeholders are aware of the activity and its potential impacts and are supportive of change and willing to consider doing what they can to aid a activity. 5 — Leading — This is the highest level of engagement. These stakeholders are fully aware of the activity and its impacts and are actively engaged to ensure the activity is successful.]
	What is the level of education of the residence?	<input type="checkbox"/> More than 50% with basic education <input type="checkbox"/> More than 50% with higher education <input type="checkbox"/> 50% with basic education and 50% with higher education